

ON THE PERFECT SQUARES IN SMARANDACHE CONCATENATED SQUARE SEQUENCE

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Abstract

Let n be positive integer, and let $s(n)$ denote the n -th Smarandache concatenated square number. In this paper we prove that if $n \equiv 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 22, \text{ or } 25 \pmod{27}$, then $s(n)$ is not a square.

In [1], Marimutha defined the Smarandache concatenated

square sequence $\{s(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ as follows:

$$(1) \quad s(1) = 1, \quad s(2) = 14, \quad s(3) = 149, \quad s(4) = 14916, \\ s(5) = 1491625, \dots$$

Then we called $s(n)$ the n -th Smarandache concatenated square number. Marimutha [1] conjectured that $s(n)$ is never a perfect square. In this paper we prove the following result:

Theorem.

If $n \equiv 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 22, \text{ or } 25 \pmod{27}$, then $s(n)$ is not a perfect square.

The above result implies that the density of perfect squares in Smarandache concatenated square sequence is at most $11/27$.

Prof of Theorem. We now assume that $s(n)$ is a perfect square.

Then we have

$$(2) \quad s(n) = x^2,$$

where x is a positive integer. Notice that $10^k \equiv 1 \pmod{9}$ for any positive integer k . We get from (1) and (2) that

$$(3) \quad s(n) \equiv 1^2 + 2^2 + \dots + n^2 \equiv 1/6 n(n+1)(2n+1) \equiv x^2 \pmod{9}.$$

It implies that

$$(4) \quad n(n+1)(2n+1) \equiv 6x^2 \pmod{27}.$$

If $n \equiv 2 \pmod{27}$, then from (4) we get $2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \equiv 6x^2 \pmod{27}$. It follows that

$$(5) \quad x^2 \equiv 5 \pmod{9}.$$

Since 5 is not a square residue mod 3, (5) is impossible.
Therefore, if $n \equiv 2 \pmod{27}$, then $s(n)$ is not a square.

By using some similarly elementary number theory methods, we can check that the congruence (4) does not hold for the remaining cases. The theorem is proved.

Reference:

- 1.H.Marimutha, "Smarandache concatenate type sequences",
Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences, 16E (1997), No. 2, 225-226.